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STUDY OF THE STATE OF THE PRACTICE OF ARTIFACTS SHARING IN HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPUTING CONFERENCES

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Chapter 1

Organization

I conducted my internship at the University of Basel in Switzerland. The University was founded in the year 1460 - being the oldest in Switzerland - and is constituted of over 13,000 students and nearly 400 professors. The president of the university is Prof. Dr. Dr. h.c. mult. Andrea Schenker-Wicki [10].

My internship took place more specifically in the High Performance Computing group. It is one of the eight computer science research groups in the Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, within the Faculty of Science of the university. The group is led by Prof. Dr. Florina M. Ciorba, and is constituted of 4 postdocs, 1 Ph.D., 1 engineer, 1 master student and 1 bachelor student [23]. Prof. Ciorba was my supervisor, along with Dr. Quentin Guilloteau, a postdoc of the group.

The research of the DMI-HPC group focuses on optimizing the performance of parallel and distributed computing systems and their applications. The organizational hierarchy is depicted in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Organizational hierarchy of the host institution of my internship

Chapter 2

Context

2.1 The process of publishing a research paper

When researchers make a new discovery, they can publish a paper describing their discovery and the experiments that led them to it. To publish a paper, the researchers first need to submit it to a conference or a trade magazine. It is then being assessed by evaluators from the conference or the magazine. If the paper meets the requirements of the evaluators, it is then accepted and published.

2.2 The "reproducibility crisis"

A survey was carried out in 2016 by Baker et al. to collect data on the state of the reproducibility of scientific experiments [4]. They asked over 1,000 researchers from diverse scientific fields multiple questions, and most of them admitted that it was hard to reproduce other researchers' experiments. Moreover, research papers reviewers are not prone to support papers that show the failure of an experiment.

This study is one of the first to have raised awareness to the "reproducibility crisis", and is one of the most well known on the topic. This "reproducibility crisis" is the origin of multiple studies on the current practices of reproducibility in many scientific fields. The study described in this report is one of them.

2.3 What is reproducibility in computer science?

According to the *Association for Computing Machinery* (ACM), there are three terms to describe the fact of obtaining the same results as the authors of a paper for a given experiment [3]:

- **Repeatability**, when the experiment is being run by the same team with the same experimental setup.

- **Reproducibility**, when the experiment is being run by a different team with the same experimental setup.
- **Replicability**, when the experiment is being run by a different team with a different experimental setup.

For this study, we focused on *reproducibility*. The ACM defined the term as follows:

*The measurement can be obtained with stated precision by a different team using the same measurement procedure, the same measuring system, under the same operating conditions, in the same or a different location on multiple trials. For computational experiments, this means that **an independent group** can obtain **the same result** using the author's own artifacts.*

What is being called artifact here is the code and the data written by the authors of the paper as a support for their experiment. According to this definition, reproducibility can only be reached when we obtain the exact same results as the authors. However, this is not always possible, as some experiments, for instance, involve measuring the performance of a distributed application. This implies that the results will contain noise, which will eventually lead to different results from one experiment to another. In that case, we satisfy ourselves with comparable results. That means that the results should statistically match the authors' results (the *KheOps* framework can be used to check if it is the case [26]).

Nearly 10 years ago, the artifacts of a paper were generally not available to the public [7]. People who wanted to reproduce the experiments needed to ask for the artifacts to the authors. Making the artifacts of an experiment available to the public is becoming a common practice since the "reproducibility crisis", but conferences and the scientific press still need to ask for it when the paper is being submitted. Even with the artifact, the reproducibility is not guaranteed. The lack of documentation, missing details on which software and hardware are required to make the artifact to run, or just that the required hardware and software is not available anymore still makes it impossible sometimes to reproduce an experiment.

2.4 How to ensure reproducibility in computer science?

First, researchers should always provide the artifact that was used to publish the results of their experiments. Along with their artifact, researchers have to provide the exact specifications of their software and hardware environment. They should also ensure the longevity of this environment, meaning that this environment should be archived, so it can be recreated years or even decades after the publication of the paper.

There are some solutions to preserve software and create reproducible software environments. For instance, *Nix* (and its most popular alternative *Guix*) is a functional package manager [20] [11]. This means that, if one uses the same Nix environment configuration in two different systems using the same operating system and CPU architecture, it will produce the exact same environment. This is ensured by the fact that Nix isolates this environment from the host system by using sandboxes, so that the Nix environment will not depend on the underlying system's specific parameters or packages.

To ensure the longevity of a Nix environment, the Nix maintainers provide archives for older versions of software, but this advantage comes with a price. In fact, to speed up the process of setting up a software environment with Nix, like with many other package managers, the maintainers are providing the users with a binary cache. This requires a lot of storage space and energy to power the data centers, which means that the cache for older packages is progressively being deleted as the storage space lowers. This means that the users need to build these packages by themselves, which requires more energy than just installing the binaries.

In addition to the software environment, the artifact's code itself should be archived on platforms such as *Software Heritage* [27]. The aim is to keep the code and data accessible even when the original Git repository is deleted, or that the hosting platform is shut down. The archived artifact should also come with a comprehensive documentation that describes the input, the output, and how to run the experiment.

The hardware, however, is more complicated to archive. It is generally recommended by some people to choose common hardware such as a x86 or ARM CPU [16], but since the specifications for these architectures are not available to the public, it is not ideal. The best solution instead would be to use open hardware, such as *RISC-V* CPUs, because they are not company dependent since their specifications are open [25]. This means that even when the last *RISC-V* CPU's production will stop, it will still be possible to produce new ones.

The general practice to assess the reproducibility of an artifact is to run it on a testbed. A testbed is a platform constituted of software and hardware configured to run reproducibility tests [28]. It can be, for instance, a high performance computer.

2.5 Why are we not there yet?

Since the "reproducibility crisis", there has been effort on making the researchers to publish reproducible artifacts. Some conferences and scientific newspapers founded evaluation boards to assess the reproduction of artifacts from submitted papers [24], but this is not enough yet. Among all the artifacts I tried to run, only half of them were working immediately: some were not compiling, and some other needed tinkering to make them work.

In fact, researchers still publish incomplete documentations on their artifacts and software/hardware environment, which makes it complicated to run them. The issue is mostly coming from a lack of education from both the researchers' and evaluators' side. Researchers also aren't motivated enough yet to create reproducible artifacts, despite the creation of reproducibility badges by the ACM (see Figure 2.1). Another reason is that some evaluation boards do not yet enforce strict enough policies on reproducibility, despite the efforts from some conferences such as *SuperComputing* that enforces authors to fill the *Artifact Evaluation and Description* forms before submitting a paper (see Figure 5.1). [15]

Figure 2.3 is a portion of an artifact's description found in a scientific paper [1]. This paper was awarded the Open Research Project badge, along with the Research Object Reviewed from the IEEE (see Figure 2.2) [6]. This means that the artifact should come with enough documentation to make it possible to reproduce it. However, we can see the lack of precision in the environment description: the artifact seemingly requires a Linux or macOS system, but it doesn't specify the version (and regarding Linux, it doesn't even specify the distribution). The same goes for Python, for which only the major version is specified, which is not enough in terms of reproducibility.

Figure 2.1: Some reproducibility badges created by the ACM. From left to right: Artifact Evaluated - Reusable (the artifact comes with enough documentation to be reproducible in theory), Artifact Available (the artifact is publicly available), Results Reproduced (the artifact has been reproduced successfully) [3].

Figure 2.2: The reproducibility badges created by the IEEE. From left to right: Open Research Objects (the artifact is publicly available), Research Objects Reviewed (the artifact comes with enough documentation to be reproducible in theory), Results Reproduced (the artifact has been reproduced successfully) [2] [6]

The required Python modules are also given without any indication on the required version.

2.6 The Docker situation

Containerization solutions such as *Docker* are being pushed by conferences such as *SuperComputing 2024* to simplify the reviewing process of artifacts [24]. In fact, Docker is a container manager that can create isolated containers running their own operating system and packages without interfering with the host OS [8]. Docker containers are easy to share, because they only require a single plain text file, named *Dockerfile*, to be rebuilt in another computer.

But a Dockerfile is not reproducible. There are indeed many reasons why building the same Dockerfile on different computers could result in a different container, or even no container at all. For instance, the Dockerfile may rely on a Docker image that has been deleted from Docker

VIII. DESCRIPTION

Link: This is our repository DOI [33]. Here's the Github link.

Description: This code base contains a DL simulation environment. To run the project, first clone the repository and cd into the project directory. The main file to run is "fdl.py".

Environment:

- Linux (preferably), MacOS, (should also run in Windows)
- Python3
- Modules: numpy, pytorch (torch, torchvision), networkx, pandas, sklearn

Figure 2.3: The description of an artifact [1]

HUB [9], or may require a package that has changed version.

To further explain the issue, let's consider the following example of a Dockerfile:

Listing 2.1: An example of a Dockerfile

```
FROM ubuntu
RUN apt install gcc
```

This Dockerfile contains multiple lines, each containing a directive. The first line contains the `FROM` directive, which tells Docker to use a specific image from Docker HUB as a base for the Docker container. Here, the Dockerfile will use Ubuntu as operating system. The second line asks Docker to run a specific shell command inside the container by using `RUN`. Here it installs the `gcc` package using the `apt` package manager.

The Docker container generated with this Dockerfile is not reproducible. In fact, the first line does not specify the version of Ubuntu that is required. By default, Docker will download the latest one, which is not the same through time. And even if a version is specified, there is no guarantee that this version will be preserved over time. A good example of images that are regularly removed from Docker HUB are the *NVIDIA CUDA* images [21].

The same issue arises with the second line. As no version is specified for `gcc`, this package will also change version through time. The only way to fix this issue is to use Nix. But Nix can be installed directly on the host operating system without losing the isolation provided by Docker, which renders Docker useless.

Docker might be a good enough solution for "short-term reproducibility", meaning that a Dockerfile provides a software environment that is reproducible for a short period. But Docker definitely is not a solution for the long-term reproducibility. One of the purposes of this study is to analyze how short this "short period" is.

Chapter 3

Tasks of the internship

The main objective of the internship was to gather research papers that use Docker, and to create a workflow that automates the building of the Docker containers of these artifacts and the analysis of the results of the builds. The experiment will run on the *Grid'5000* french testbed [5].

The final product is based on a proof of concept written by Dr. Guilloteau called *ECG* [12]. The name is an acronym of the word *electrocardiogram*, because like an electrocardiogram, the script written for this proof of concept checks if a container is "alive". In our case, a container that is alive is a container that can still be built.

This initial version, which is a Python script, is only able to build the Docker containers, but not to generate logs for the results. My task was to build the input for this script, improve this script by implementing the logging of errors that could occur during the build, generating the list of packages installed inside the container, analyze and plot those results.

Dr. Guilloteau and I worked jointly on this study.

3.1 Research questions

The purpose of this analysis is to show why Docker itself (as well as other container managers) is not a solution for long-term reproducibility, and that the current usage of Docker is suboptimal for this purpose. We want to show the evolution through time of multiple components constituting the artifact: the Docker container, the software environment generated by this container, and the evolution of the archive containing the artifact's code and assets. Thus, our study will try to answer the following question:

How is the software environment of an artifact relying on a Docker container varying through time?

To answer this question, we will have to answer the following study questions a few months after the experiment has started:

- Are the artifacts still available?

- Have the artifacts changed? How frequently?
- Have some base Docker images required by the containers been removed? How frequently?
- Have the containers' packages changed in version? How frequently?
- Are some packages required by the containers not available anymore? How frequently does it happen?

3.2 Proposed approach

We designed a workflow to collect data that should enable us to answer our study questions.

The first part of the workflow is to gather artifacts that use Docker. We selected specific HPC conferences, such as *EuroPar 2024* and *SuperComputing 2024*, as a base for our set of artifacts. Since the papers for these conferences have not been submitted yet, we ran our tests on artifacts from older conferences, such as *Principles and Practice of Parallel Programming 2023*.

The second part is to periodically build the Docker images of these artifacts. The period in question is not defined yet. The execution frequency of the build script should be low enough to limit the energy costs of the experiment, but also high enough to capture all the behaviors of the Docker containers. According to the Nyquist-Shannon sampling theorem [22], the sampling rate should be chosen between the lowest and the highest possible frequencies. Based on empirical estimations, packages usually have a new update every 6 months at least, and multiple times a day at most. Thus, we think that building the Docker images every month is a good starting point. After the first year, however, the frequency should be reduced. This workflow is indeed expected to be consuming a lot of energy, so we do not want to run it too frequently if not necessary.

The build process should output multiple files:

- List of the packages installed in the container.
- Log of the artifact hash.
- Log of the build status.

The list of the packages takes into account as many package sources as possible. This includes package managers such as `dpkg` or `pip`, but also packages downloaded from a Git repository using the `git` command, and packages obtained from the web using neither a package manager nor Git, that we decided to call *miscellaneous (misc.) packages* (in general, these packages are downloaded using commands like `curl` or `wget`).

The log of the artifact hash gives us information on potential changes on the content of the artifact's archive published by the authors. In the other hand, the log of the build status gives us a quick summary on the error that caused the build to fail, or just a mention that the build was a success otherwise.

The last part is the analysis. This part will rely on the outputs of the previous part, in order to perform analysis and to draw plots. We identified three categories of analysis:

- Software environment
- Build status
- Artifact modifications

The software environment analysis focuses on the popularity of the package sources, in one hand, and on the variation of the packages inside the container, in the other hand. The build status analysis aims at measuring the amount of Docker containers that build successfully or fail to build. For failed builds, the analysis also gives the amount of containers that encountered each type of error. Similarly, the artifact analysis measures the amount of artifacts that are still available or not, and the amount of artifacts that have been modified.

3.3 Implementation

The workflow is implemented using *Snakemake* [18]. Snakemake is an implementation of *Make* that facilitates the development of workflows and the management of the input/output of each part of the workflow. It can also be used on high performance computers to start multiple instances of a program on multiple computing nodes in parallel. The software environment of the workflow can be recreated using the Nix package manager.

The following sections will detail every part of the workflow. A schema of the workflow is also available in Figure 5.2.

3.3.1 Artifact configuration

In order to build the container of the artifact, we need configuration files to tell the building script notably where to download the artifact, how to build the container and which package sources are being used in the container.

We decided to write the configuration files in the *Nickel* language [19]. In contrast to description languages, such as JSON, Nickel is a configuration language that allows us to write checking functions in the description file to enforce specific values on the fields. For instance, we restricted the possible values for the package managers to only the one we actually track in the building script. This allows us to catch potential errors as early as possible, to save debugging time. The checking functions are called contracts, and they can also be written to a separate file, which is what we did.

In our workflow, we give the artifact configuration and the contract to the Nickel interpreter. If no errors have been found, the interpreter outputs the configuration file in the JSON format. It can then be given to the building script, since it is certified to contain no errors.

The following is a portion of an example of an artifact configuration file. Here, the artifact's container relies on two package managers: `dpkg` and `pip`.

Listing 3.1: An example of an artifact configuration file

```
{  
  version = "1.0",
```

```

    artifact_url = "http://localhost.com/artifact.zip",
    type = "zip",
    virtualization = "docker",
    buildfile_dir = "./",
    package_managers = [ "dpkg", "pip" ],
}

```

The following portion of the Nickel contract enforces specific values (written in the array named `PACKAGE MANAGERS`) for the array that contains the package managers used in the artifact's container:

Listing 3.2: A portion of the Nickel contract

```

let
  conf = {
    PACKAGE MANAGERS = ["dpkg", "rpm", "pacman", "pip", "conda"],
  }
in
{
  PackageManager = std.contract.from_predicate (
    fun value => std.array.any (fun x => x == value) conf.
      PACKAGE MANAGERS
  ),
  Artifact = {
    package_managers
      | Array PackageManager,
  }
}

```

3.3.2 The building script (ECG)

Like in the original version, the building script is called *ECG*. As said above, *ECG* takes as an input a JSON configuration file. It also takes the paths to where it should store the output files. *ECG* uses these parameters to build the Docker container, and then to output the result.

The output files are a list of the installed packages, the log of the build status, a log of the hash of the artifact's archive, and the log of the script itself. The list of installed packages is being written to a CSV file, as well as the build status and the artifact hash log. The script's output is a simple plain text file that can be used for manual debugging. This file is not generated by *ECG* itself, but rather by the workflow manager.

The package list will include, not only the name of the packages, but also the version and the package manager they have been installed with. The build status will include the name of the artifact, the timestamp of when the status is being registered, and the result. This status can be a success, or a type of error, such as a package that couldn't be installed, or the base Docker image that couldn't be found. Finally, the artifact hash log will just include the timestamp of when the artifact has been downloaded, and its hash. The build status is retrieved by the workflow manager to populate the blacklist. This blacklist contains all artifacts that failed to build, and is used to filter the list of artifacts to build. The purpose is to save energy and time by skipping some artifacts if we know that they will not build.

We do not append outputs of consecutive executions of ECG to the same file. Instead, all output files are stored under a separate folder for each execution of ECG. This ensures that they are not modified if ECG is run again. It also makes the workflow functional, because we do not rely on the previous state of a file when writing the outputs. This part is not managed by ECG itself, but rather by the workflow manager.

The following is an example of a package list as outputted by ECG:

Listing 3.3: An example of a package list

```
ubuntu-keyring,2023.11.28.1,dpkg,test,1723129517.304291
util-linux,2.39.3-9ubuntu6,dpkg,test,1723129517.304291
xauth,1:1.1.2-1build1,dpkg,test,1723129517.304291
zlib1g:amd64,1:1.3.dfsg-3.1ubuntu2,dpkg,test,1723129517.304291
pkg1,f78a0d8e81bca21b7df794d51069c0b10a94c5,git,test
,1723129517.304291
```

The first column is the name of the package, the second is the version, and the third is the source of the package. The version is fetched from the package manager. In case of Git packages, however, the hash of the latest commit is taken as a version number. Similarly, for misc. packages, it is the hash of the downloaded package that is used as version number. The two last columns, respectively the name of the artifact and the timestamp of the package list, are being used later for the analysis.

3.3.3 The analysis scripts

For each type of analysis (explained in Section 3.2) that is being performed on the outputs provided by ECG, there is a dedicated analysis script.

The software analysis script has two modes: *sources stats* and *packages changes*. The first mode will count the number of packages for each package source. The second mode will cross multiple package lists generated over time to compare the consecutive versions of each package of an artifact's container. It will use this information to count the number of packages for which the version has changed over time.

The build status analysis script will count the number of containers that have been built, and for the ones that have failed, the number of containers for each category of error. The artifact analysis script will count the number of artifacts that are available or unavailable, and the number of artifacts that have changed over time.

All of these scripts take as input the output of either a single execution of ECG, resulting in an analysis of the current status, or of multiple executions, resulting in an analysis of the evolution between two time points. The only exceptions are the analysis of the changes of packages' version, and the analysis of artifacts changes, which require outputs of multiple executions to generate meaningful results.

The output of each of these scripts is a table with a column for each category of the topic being measured. It can be package sources, build or artifact statuses, depending on the analysis being run. Like ECG, the outputs of the analysis scripts are stored in separate files for every execution.

Listing 3.4: An example of the table of the number of packages per source for a single artifact, generated by the software analysis script in *sources stats* mode

```
260, 0, 0, 3, 0, 1, 1, 1723565625.986356
```

In the above example, the columns are respectively: `dpkg`, `rpm`, `pacman`, `pip`, `conda`, `git`, `misc`. The last column is the timestamp, used to plot these results at the correct time. The analysis found 260 `dpkg` packages, 3 `pip` packages, one package obtained using Git and a `misc` package.

Plotting

The tables generated by the analysis script are then plotted using the plotting script written in R. This script can generate either a line plot or a bar plot. For this study, we want to generate the following plots:

1. Number of packages per source.
2. Number of build results per category (either "success", or the error category).
3. Number of artifact status per category (either "available" or "unavailable", and if it was modified over time).
4. Number of packages that changed version per source.

All the above will be plotted as lines, to show the evolution over the time. The first four plots will also be plotted as bars, to show either the current status, or an evolution, like on a line plot, but on a reduced set of time points. This could be used to show the evolution across multiple years.

Figure 3.1 shows the evolution of packages' version through time for a single artifact. Even though we just started the experiment, we already see that 17 `dpkg` packages have been updated since the 9th of August 2024.

Figure 3.2 shows the amount of packages per package source for a single artifact. The tallest rectangle represents the number of packages installed through `dpkg`, which is 260. The three other rectangles represent the number of `pip`, Git and `misc` packages, which are respectively 3, 1 and 1. This plot represents the state of only a single time point, but other time points can be added to allow comparisons between the states at multiple time points.

These plots are not very meaningful yet, especially the bar plot, because it is only based on measures from one artifact. But after a few months, we can expect more representative results.

Figure 3.1: Number of packages that changed version per package source for a single artifact. The x -axis represents the time, the y -axis represents the number of packages, and the categories are package sources.

Figure 3.2: Number of packages installed per source for a single artifact. The x -axis represents the time, the y -axis represents the number of packages. Each rectangle is a package source.

Chapter 4

Conclusion

4.1 Assessment of the work

Overall, the workflow is running well. The checking of the configuration files, the building script, the analysis scripts and the plotting script are working without any issue for now.

Regarding the results of the study, it is still early to assess them yet. This is an experiment on the long term, so it will take some months, maybe years, to have initial results. However, the first build errors are already showing up, as some Docker containers already rely on deleted base images, or that some packages are not being installed successfully.

A Gantt chart of the tasks completed during the internship can be found on Figure 5.3.

4.2 Difficulties

My first task before working on the study itself was to try to run the code of some artifacts by myself. This was not straightforward. The first reason is that I am a beginner in HPC, so I am still having trouble understanding the artifact and its input/output. The second reason is because of the missing documentation and the incomplete software environment description provided with most of the artifacts I tried. I only worked on four artifacts, but it took me several days to make them run, when it was possible.

For instance, when I tried to run the artifact mentioned in Section 2.5, I had a hard time recreating the software environment, either because a specific version of a library was required, but not specified, or because the specified version was not the right one. There was another artifact that required NVIDIA CUDA to run, but I kept facing errors when trying to compile it, so I gave up.

There also were difficulties when working on the study. The first was that the methods for getting new packages are very different from one Dockerfile to another. And even if the package sources are generally the same (most popular sources being `dpkg`, `pip` or `Git`), the actual process of downloading and installing the package vary. For instance, some people will directly use `Git` to download a `Git` package, but will then remove the `.git` folder. Some other people will download a `Git` package without even using the `git` command but rather `wget/curl`, which

sometimes results in a missing `.git` folder as well. This complicates the process of finding the hash of the latest commit, thus the version number of the package, since it is stored in the `.git` folder. Taking into account plenty of package managers was also cumbersome, because they all work differently. I had to adapt the commands to fetch the package lists to all package managers that have been selected for the study, which are: `dpkg`, `pip`, `conda`, `rpm`, `pacman`.

The analysis was also a long part of the study. Finding what to analyze and how is not obvious, and requires asking oneself the right questions. It also takes some time to find how to plot the analysis to show meaningful information. The structure of the analysis process itself is hard to determine and to integrate with the rest of the workflow. Thinking about the input/output, the analysis scripts to write, and their purpose, took me a few days to figure out. And the functional paradigm of the workflow did not help. Since every execution of ECG results in a different output file, it is impossible to fetch the relevant information from a single file: it has to be reconstituted.

4.3 Potential improvements

The code that we wrote for this study can be improved in many ways. First, there is no support for container managers other than Docker. We decided to only support Docker for now, because it is the most popular container manager among HPC conferences' artifacts. However, some artifacts are also using *Singularity*. Adding support for Singularity would not only enable support for more artifacts (though not a lot), but would also support researchers that choose open source containerization solutions over proprietary ones such as Docker.

The writing of configuration files for hundreds of artifacts being too cumbersome for only two people, we have to involve other people in this project. This implies writing a protocol on how to write configuration files that can be used by people who would like to join us. A draft of this protocol can be found in the project's repository, under the directory `protocol` [14] [13].

Currently, artifacts for which the Docker container fails to build once are blacklisted forever. But there could be cases where a container fails to build only once. For these cases, we need to give those artifacts at least a second chance. An improvement would be to make the workflow manager to try to build the Docker containers of the blacklisted artifacts again, on a regular basis.

Finally, the analysis part has not been integrated to the workflow yet, so it has to be run manually. This is an essential part of the project, so it will have to be fixed before the first execution of the workflow.

Since this report has to be handed in before the end of my internship, some above-mentioned features (and maybe more) may be implemented before the final presentation. In that case, the improvements will be clarified during the presentation.

4.4 Lessons learned

This internship was an opportunity to learn a lot of lessons. The first and most important one is the challenge of reproducibility. As I tried to explain in this report, reproducibility is not obvious. It takes efforts to create artifacts that are reproducible, and not everybody wants to take the time of evaluating the reproducibility of one's own artifact. The short deadlines for paper submissions are a reason why the effort is only partial, but this is also a question of education. Most researchers are still not trained on how to make their artifacts reproducible, and sometimes they are not aware of the good practices either. The major challenge of reproducibility is to restore people's trust in science by making the researcher's work more valuable.

Some other lessons are more practical. For instance, I learned how to run programs that require high performance and parallelization on a shared cluster, and how to develop a workflow for an experiment. I also discovered how scientific artifacts are written, shared and evaluated, and I could notice that the current practices do not ensure reproducibility. The coding part of my internship allowed me to learn new languages and tools, such as Nix, Nickel and R, and to improve my knowledge with Python, Docker and operating systems in general.

Outside the study itself, this internship was an occasion for me to have an initial overview on the environment of a research lab. My work also involved collaboration with other people, which improved my team work skills. And finally, since I was in a research team where English is the main language, and that English is not my native language (as for the other team members), I could also improve my language skills during my internship.

Chapter 5

Appendix

Appendix: Artifact Description/Artifact Evaluation

Artifact Description (AD)

I. OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND ARTIFACTS

A. Paper's Main Contributions

Provide a list of all main contributions of the paper.

- C_1 This is the 1st contribution.
- C_2 This is the 2nd contribution.
- C_3 This is the 3rd contribution.

B. Computational Artifacts

List the computational artifacts related to this paper along with their respective DOIs. Note that all computational artifacts may be archived under a single DOI.

- A_1 <https://doi.org/YY.YYYY/zenodo.0XXXXXX>
- A_2 <https://doi.org/ZZ.YYYY/zenodo.1XXXXXX>
- A_3 <https://doi.org/ZZ.YYYY/zenodo.2XXXXXX>

Provide a table with the relevant computational artifacts, highlight their relation to the contributions (from above) and point to the elements in the paper that are reproducible by each artifact, e.g., which figures or tables were generated with the artifact.

Artifact ID	Contributions Supported	Related Paper Elements
A_1	C_1	Tables 1-2 Figure 3
A_2	C_2	Tables 2-3 Figures 1-2
..		

II. ARTIFACT IDENTIFICATION

Provide the following six subsections for each computational artifact A_i .

A. Computational Artifact A_1

Relation To Contributions

Briefly explain the relationship between the artifact and contributions.

Expected Results

Provide a higher level description of what outcome to expect from the corresponding experiments. Provide an explanation of how the results substantiate the main contributions.

Algorithm A should be faster than Algorithms C and B in all GPU scenarios.

Expected Reproduction Time (in Minutes)

Estimate the time required to reproduce the artifact, providing separate estimates for the individual steps: Artifact Setup, Artifact Execution, and Artifact Analysis.

The expected computational time of this artifact on GPU X is 20 min.

Artifact Setup (incl. Inputs)

Hardware: Specify the hardware requirements and dependencies (e.g., a specific interconnect or GPU type is required).

Software: Introduce all required software packages, including the computational artifact. For each software package, specify the version and provide the URL.

Datasets / Inputs: Describe the datasets required by the artifact. Indicate whether the datasets can be generated, including instructions, or if they are available for download, providing the corresponding URL.

Installation and Deployment: Detail the requirements for compiling, deploying, and executing the experiments, including necessary compilers and their versions.

Artifact Execution

Provide an abstract description of the experiment workflow of the artifact. It is important to identify the main tasks (processes) and how they depend on each other.

A workflow may consist of three tasks: T_1 , T_2 , and T_3 . The task T_1 may generate a specific dataset. This dataset is then used as input by a computational task T_2 , and the output of T_2 is processed by another task T_3 , which produces the final results (e.g., plots, tables, etc.). State the individual tasks T_i and provide their dependencies, e.g., $T_1 \rightarrow T_2 \rightarrow T_3$.

Provide details on the experimental parameters. How and why were parameters set to a specific value (if relevant for the reproduction of an artifact), e.g., size of dataset, number of data points, input sizes, etc. Additionally, include details on statistical parameters, like the number of repetitions.

Artifact Analysis (incl. Outputs)

B. Computational Artifact A_2

Provide the same type of information as done for Computational Artifact A_1 .

Figure 5.1: The template of the Artifact Description/Evaluation form that has to be filled by the author of a paper that is being submitted for the *SuperComputing 2024* conference [17]

Workflow manager (Snakemake)

Figure 5.2: A schema of the Snakemake workflow

Figure 5.3: Gantt chart of the tasks of the internship

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